

pH-metric and electronic spectral studies on Schiff base complex formation with some 3d-metal ions

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Manuscript received 17 July 2000, revised 19 October 2000, accepted 16 December 2000

Equilibrium-based computer models on eight Schiff base complex systems, viz. Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Cu^{II}/Zn^{II}-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (A)-L-threonine(thr) and L-glutamine(gln) (B) systems demonstrate the formation of Schiff base complexes of stoichiometry MAB, MA₂B and MA₂B₂. The Schiff base (AB) binds the metal ion in a tridentate manner. Tetrahedral geometry for CoAB and NiAB, square-planar geometry for CuAB and octahedral geometry for M(AB)₂ complexes are indicated.

In continuation of our earlier work on the solution equilibria of Schiff base complexes of transition metal ions^{1,2}, we report here the solution equilibria involved in the Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Cu^{II}/Zn^{II}-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde(pyal)(A)-L-threonine(thr) and L-glutamine(gln) (B) systems.

Results and Discussion

In addition to the binary species HA, MA, MA₂, HB, H₂B, MB and MB₂, three types of ternary complexes of stoichiometry MAB, MA₂B and MA₂B₂ have been detected in the Co^{II}/Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-thr and gln(B) systems, while only MAB type of species has been found to be present in the Cu^{II} systems.

The preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary species can be illustrated by considering stepwise formation constants of the various species formed (Tables 1 and 2). Such a case in Co^{II}-pyal(A)-thr(B) system is given below :

The log β_{MAB} values (Table 2) in the M^{II}-pyal(A)-thr and gln(B) (M = Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) systems are found to be higher than the statistically calculated³ values, if the ligands were considered to coordinate the metal ion independently forming mixed ligand complexes. The higher experimental values can be explained by considering the interligand interaction between the CHO group of pyal and amino group of thr/gln to form a tridentate Schiff base in-

volving pyridine and imino nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen atoms resulting the formation of two five-membered chelates. Again, the log β_{MAB} values (Table 2) in the systems with B = thr and glu are higher than those in the systems with B = L-valine² by 0.40 log units. This enhancement of stability is too low for considering the involvement of the alcoholic group of thr or amide group of gln also in coordination. The higher stability can probably be accounted by considering the presence of molecular recognition between the free hydroxyl/amide groups of the neighbouring complex species leading to molecular association through intermolecular hydrogen bonding. Such a type of molecular recognition has also been reported earlier^{1,2,5}.

The species distribution diagrams for all the M(II)-pyal(A)-thr and glu(B) systems indicate that the Schiff base complex formation is favoured over the binary species. The CoAB species predominates between pH 7.0 and 8.0, reaching a maximum of 60% of the total metal ion. The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} systems also follow similar trend. In the Cu^{II} systems, the CuAB species is predominantly present between pH 5.4 and 7.0 and reaches to a maximum extent of 75%.

The electronic spectrum, recorded at pH 7.54 in the 1 : 1 system for Co^{II}-pyal(A)-gln(B) shows a peak at 695 nm. This corresponds to the tetrahedral environment of the ligand field around Co^{II} due to ⁴A₂(F) → ⁴T₁(P) transition⁶, indicating the presence of CoAB species with tetrahedral geometry. The NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-gln(B) system at pH 7.81 shows intense absorption at 679 nm, which corresponds to the transition ³T₁(F) → ³T₁(P), showing tetrahedral geometry for NiAB. Again, the broad band at 646 nm recorded at pH 5.5 in the 1 : 1 system in Cu^{II}-

Note

Table 1. Stability constants for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with pyal, thr and gln (A)*

Parameters	Co ^{II}			Ni ^{II}			Cu ^{II}			Zn ^{II}		
	pyal	thr	gln	pyal	thr	gln	pyal	thr	gln	pyal	thr	gln
log β _{MA}	1.75	4.75	4.44	1.98	5.42	5.17	2.65	7.96	7.74	1.67	4.72	4.55
log β _{MA₂}	3.45	8.65	8.07	3.90	9.76	9.45	4.79	14.39	14.20	3.27	8.50	8.35
log β _{HA}	3.84	2.29	2.17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
log β _{H₂A}	-	9.03	9.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*thr and gln become ligand B in Schiff base complex systems.

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 4.

Table 2. Stability constants for the ternary Schiff base complexes in M^{II}-pyal(A)-thr and gln(B) systems*

Parameters	Co ^{II}		Ni ^{II}		Cu ^{II}		Zn ^{II}	
	thr	gln	thr	gln	thr	gln	thr	gln
log β _{MAB}	10.61 (6.65)	10.65 (6.06)	11.93 (7.13)	11.91 (6.98)	17.76 (9.99)	17.71 (9.90)	10.72 (6.19)	10.69 (6.11)
log β _{MA₂B}	13.01 (8.08)	13.05 (7.79)	14.63 (9.08)	14.56 (8.93)	-	-	13.02 (7.82)	13.01 (7.75)
log β _{MA₂B₂}	17.15 (12.40)	16.76 (11.82)	19.69 (13.96)	19.25 (13.65)	-	-	17.93 (12.07)	17.49 (11.92)

*The values in the parentheses are the calculated³ log β values for the simple mixed ligand complexes without interligand interaction.

pyal(A)-gln(B) shows square-planar geometry for CuAB species.

The log β values obtained for MA₂B complexes in the M^{II}-pyal(A)-thr and gln(B) systems are much higher than those calculated³ for simple mixed ligand complexes without interligand interaction. The higher experimental values clearly points MA₂B species to the Schiff base complex and can be represented as M(AB)A, in which (AB) binds tridentately through pyridine and imino nitrogen and the carboxylato oxygen atoms, while (A) coordinating through pyridine nitrogen alone¹.

The log β values for the MA₂B₂ complexes in the M^{II}-pyal(A)-thr and gln(B) systems (Table 2) are much higher than theoretically calculated³ values for simple mixed ligand complexes. This shows that they are bis(Schiff base) complexes and can be described as Co(AB)₂ and both (AB) would bind the metal ion in a tridentate mode. The M(AB)₂ complexes are found to be present at higher concentrations in the 1 : 2 systems near pH 8.0. The spectrum of Co(AB)₂ in the Co^{II}-pyal(A)-gln(B) system measured at pH 7.80 shows a low intensity band at 730 nm and high intensity peak at 532 nm, corresponding to the transitions⁶ of Co^{II} in an octahedral environment, viz. ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (730 nm), ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{1g}(P) (532 nm). Hence an octahedral geometry can be assigned to Co(AB)₂. The spectrum at pH 7.95 in 1 : 2 system of Ni^{II}-pyal(A)-gln(B) shows three peaks with λ_{max} values of 899, 623 and 379 nm. These correspond to the d-d transition of Ni^{II} in an octahedral environment of ligand field indicating octahedral geometry for Ni(AB)₂.

Experimental

Metal nitrates (AnalaR) were used. Pure grade pyal ligand (from Lancaster) was further purified by distilling twice under reduced pressure. The amino acids were obtained from Fluka. The equilibrium attained only slowly in the Schiff base complex systems and hence a batchwise titration method was adopted^{1,2}. The calculations were carried out with the help of a computer program⁷ designed for the evaluation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The auxiliary data for the binary complexes used under the present experimental conditions^{1,4} (Table 1) were fixed as non-refinable parameters during the computation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The equipment used for pH-titrations and electronic spectral measurements were the same as described earlier^{1,2}. All the experiments were carried out at 25° and I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃).

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